

SOME CHALLENGES IN TEACHING LANGUAGES.

Yarmatova Yulduz Ravshanovna

Senior English teacher of
Uzbek language and literature Department of
Termez Institute of Engineering and Technology

Omonov Islom Shukhrat o'gli

Student of Termez Institute of Engineering and Technology
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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on the deep understanding of CLT in the field of English Language Teaching field in the Uzbekistan context. The article is written in good English and presents the views, analysis of teaching based on the experiences of the author. The content of the article illustrates the understanding of the author about the implementation of CLT in teacher's context.

Teaching and learning foreign languages in Uzbekistan has become very essential and global process since the first days of the Independence of our country. It pays much attention to the increasing of educational level of people, their intellectual knowledge. Nowadays, English is worth not just knows, but it is worth really knowing. There is a great importance role to understand modern English in order to make a conversation people who live in foreign countries. Many directions are being implemented to improve the reformation of foreign language in our country. Remodeling the system of teaching is to put biggest responsibilities in front of the teacher who teaches at school, at universities, and colleges. Reforming the teaching system into CEFR is also the main factor to develop the teaching foreign language. The modernization considers new requirements for teaching staff; e.g. they should present good knowledge in foreign languages and IT skills apart from their professional subject(s). Study programmes are revised and updated taking into account changing labour market requirements.

In the context of broad international relations with other countries, it is important to communicate with foreign specialists, develop professional and business contacts with foreign partners and colleagues, and read various publications in a foreign language. Recently, there has been a growing demand for the study of a foreign language, not only in higher education institutions, but also in schools, especially in professionally oriented classes. Demand will grow in the years to come. This is explained by the fact that the number of educators who study a foreign language for general communication is reduced. Educational institutions are increasingly coming to the conclusion about the advisability of learning a foreign language by profession. The goal of teaching a foreign language in higher education institutions is to master a foreign language as a means of communication, and to acquire professionally-directed foreign-language competence for the successful performance of further professional activities.

I work as an ESP teacher and I faced many challenges in teaching English as a second language. The challenge that I have found to be among the biggest are the culture of the learners, an individual's own bad habits and right teaching material.

The general personality of learners is shy and afraid to make mistakes. These are very bad traits when it comes to learning a new language. Getting my students to overcome these tendencies never ceases to be a challenge.

Another challenge is working around the memory of the learner. If a person has weak skills in remembering new information, then we need to get them to work on strengthening that area of their intellect.

Another challenge is laziness and lack of motivation. My best and most amazing students are the ones who are absolutely sold out to learning the language and obsess over it. I see most of my students once weekly for one hour. The rest of the week is up to them how much time they spend working on the language. I never need to cajole or prod or push those who are fanatical about gaining this new language. If a student is not motivated, there is very little I can do to change that.

Another challenge to overcome is dealing with the student who does not like being corrected. This person resists correction. They may learn the language, but with plenty of mistakes. This type of personality is difficult for any teacher to deal with.

Another challenge is a student who learns unevenly. By this I mean the student learns grammar and can do exercises just fine. This student also can monologue without too many problems. But when it comes to listening and comprehension of the spoken language, they are completely lost. Getting the student to switch to being more balanced is a regular challenge when teaching.

Dealing with a student's preconceived idea that they will become totally fluent after a minimal number of lessons is always a skill all ESL teachers will need.

The above are the problems on the student's part. Now let me focus on what the teacher has control over if he or she is teaching privately. This is the selection of material for use in teaching. Most students do not choose this themselves, but leave it up to the teacher. Finding material that is at the correct level of difficulty and will keep the student's attention is a challenge.

I teach privately, but I have taught groups of students both at language schools and at a public gymnasium/high school, and middle school. Curriculum choice was always a major challenge. The groups were ALWAYS multi-level or mixed ability, some with very vast differences in ability. Classroom management can also be an issue for the ESL teacher.

There are many challenges which might make the job uncomfortable, but none of these can extinguish the joy the teacher feels when a student gains a skill or ability that no one thought was possible or gets a report from a parent that you have helped the child overcome their shyness in speaking and using their new language. It makes all the challenges seem like trifles.

There are a lot of principles that teachers of EFL can employ to learn how to teach language better. These principles might help language teachers gain an 'all-important ability to comprehend when to use a technique. As a teacher I use some principles in my classes.

First of all I try to encourage contact between students and faculty. Building rapport with students is very important. The contact between students and teachers are vital to the

students' success. We know that faculty have many avenues to follow to open up the lines of communication.

The next principle which I use is to develop reciprocity and cooperation among students. When students are encouraged to work as a team, more learning takes place. Characteristics of good learning are collaborative and social, not competitive and isolated. Working together improves thinking and understanding. For the regular classroom I use cooperative learning groups.

The third principle is to encourage active learning. Learning is an active process. Students are not able to learn much by only sitting in classes listening to teachers, memorizing pre-packaged assignments, and churning out answers. They must be able to talk about what they are learning, write about it, relate it to past experiences, and apply it to their daily lives. Students need to make learning a part of themselves. For the regular classroom I ask students to relate what they are learning to something in real life. I use journaling. I give students concrete, real-life situations to analyze.

Principle 4: Giving prompt feedback. By knowing what you know and do not know gives a focus to learning. In order for students to benefit from courses, they need appropriate feedback on their performance. When starting out, students need help in evaluating their current knowledge and capabilities. Within the classroom, students need frequent opportunities to perform and receive suggestions for improvement. Throughout their time in college and especially at the end of their college career, students need chances to reflect on what they have learned, what they still need to know, and how to assess themselves. For the regular classroom we can use follow-up presentations with a five minute period for students to write down what they have learned in class. I provide informative comments that show the students' errors and give suggestions on how they can improve.

Principle 5: Respect diverse talents and ways of learning. There are many different ways to learn and no two people learn the same way. Students bring different talents and learning styles to the classroom. Students that excel in the seminar room may be all thumbs in the lab or art studio and vice versa. Students need the opportunity to show their talents and learn in ways that work for them. Then, they can be guided into new ways of learning that are not as easy for them. For the regular classroom we can use Web technologies to allow students to pick and choose learning experiences that fits the way they learn. We should encourage students to speak up when they do not understand. We also can use diverse teaching activities and techniques to address a broad range of students. We should select readings and design activities related to the background of students.

Teaching by principles will empower us as a professional: being able to justify your choice of certain techniques appropriate for your students, monitor yourself while implementing them and evaluating their effectiveness, and making decisions on how to improve or adapt them to address your students' needs.

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